

DATABASES ANALYSIS OF HYDROPOWER RESOURCE POTENTIAL AROUND THE GLOBE

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ABSTRACT

The renewable generation is one of the fast growing power system .Whereas the world is facing the challenge of effectively exploiting and utilizing renewable energy resources, not only to meet the increasing energy demand, but also to preserve and to reduce the depletion of fossil fuels and to lessen the amount of CO2 emissions in our atmosphere .The national energy generation resources of every country plays an important role in the development. The energy transition is well underway in most European countries. It has a growing impact on electric power systems as it dramatically modifies the way electricity is produced. In this paper, our focus is to perform a systematic review of hydropower resource potential around the Globe. In this study we will address three research queries: 1) what is the existing status of hydropower resource potential around the globe? 2) What kind of methodologies frameworks and approaches are used for exploiting and utilizing renewable energy resources 3) What are the limitations of exploiting renewable resource potentials. The purpose of the study is to highlight the current research issues, to provide valid solutions to these issues and to find out the limitations of existing work in this area of hydropower resource potential. This will be done by performing quantitative literature analysis of different databases and all the results will be gathered by analysing the statistical data using "SPSS". Remedial techniques for handling the limitation of usability engineering management will be planned in future.

KEYWORDS

Sustainable energy resource; Hydroelectricity; Renewable energy source; Sustainable hydropower; Hydroelectric energy; Hydropower technology ; Hydroelectric power Hydropower; Resource potential; Systematic study of hydropower; Database analysis of resource potential; Resource potential around the globe

1. INTRODUCTION

Lack of latest power generation techniques leads to unavailability of electricity to the population and they depend on traditional systems. According to the study, it was revealed that more than 1.27 billion people worldwide do not have access to electricity in 2010 [1]. Almost all countries around the world have recognized the importance of dominance which is to be self-sufficient for power generation and management. To deal with the universal scatter gap, the power system must undergo an insurgency that specializes in learning about the transition from fossil fuels to renewable energy. Long ago, meeting the electricity demand through adequate supply of electricity was a major problem. This is a major task for renovating the power network that is responsible for the supply, because of the extraordinary inadequacies, the inability of management to cope with the backing mechanism that leads to serious issues of "circular debt", land imbalances Near recovery and impractical electrical costs [2]]. Energy consumption has grown rapidly in the last decade globally and is projected to increase by 33% from 2010 to 2030 [3]. Lack of fossil fuel resources is a major threat to the world economy and is a factor. Today the world faces the most important economic, environmental and developmental issues. The energy sector accounts for 75% of global GHG emissions [4]. The steady increase in global energy demand has led to an increase in carbon dioxide (CO₂) emissions and is a serious impact

to the environment and a significant contributor to global climate change. The relationship between renewable and non-renewable energy sources, economic development, and CO₂ emissions has been investigated in several studies. Many people have used panel country data to examine these relationships. For example, Apergis and Payne [5] studied 80 countries and found bidirectional causalities between renewable energy consumption and economic growth and between non-renewable energy consumption and economic growth. Hydroelectric power generation contributes about 16% of global electricity generation [6]. In 2010 it produced three-fourths of all global renewable electricity. Large and small hydro contributed 70% and 6% with half the production coming from China, Brazil, United States, Canada and Russia respectively. In some countries, including Brazil and many African countries, 75% of grid electricity comes from hydro.

In study, systematic review research questions are worked by the "PICOC" structure against research question look into strings are worked for various query strings including various databases, "IEEE, ACM", "GOOGLE SCHOLAR" and "SCIENCE DIRECT". Databases are made against each query strings and query protocol is implemented on the databases for conclusive assurance of papers, with assistance of "data extraction frames" information from each chosen paper is extricated and checked on statistically

2. PROTOCOL FOR SEARCH PROCESS

Consequent to deciding inquire about questions a survey convention is created which consolidates the accompanying:

- The Search Process
- "Inclusion" & "Exclusion" Criteria
- The Selection Procedure
- The Data Extraction Process
- Data Synthesis

3. SOURCES FOR LITERATURE SEARCH

Hydropower resource potential is a wide and intrigue field with conflicting terminologies. We searched "Springer", "IEEE", "Science Direct" and "ACM" for primary studies

4. LITERATURE SEARCH STRATEGY

4.1 Research Question in PICOC Structure

- I. RQ1: What is the existing status of hydropower resource potential around the globe?
 - *Population: Citizens*
 - *Intervention: Hydropower resource Potential management*
 - *Outcome: Status of Hydropower Resource Potential around the globe*

1) Search Strings/Second Step: Synonyms

a) Population

"Citizens

b) Intervention

“Resource potential Management”, “Hydropower resource potential management approaches”, “Hydropower resource potential Evaluation”, “Hydropower resource potential development approaches” “Hydropower resource potential development techniques”

c) Outcome

“Hydropower trends around the Globe” , “Resource Potential Status”, “Status of Resource Potential Management”, “Current Resource Potential Status”, “Hydropower Resource Potential status”, ”Hydropower Resource Potential Trends and Status”

2) Strings Used for Essential “Primary” Studies Search of Research Question 1

Table 1: Strings used for primary studies search of the existing status of hydropower resource potential around the globe

Database	Search String
Springer	“Resource potential Management”, “Hydropower resource potential management approaches” , “Hydropower resource potential Evaluation”, “Hydropower resource potential development approaches” “Hydropower resource potential development techniques”, “Hydropower resource potential measurement”, “Resource Potential”, “Hydropower resource potential Analysis”, “Resource potential management methodologies”, “Hydropower resource potential methodologies”, “Resource potential Essentials”, “Resource potential methods”, “Resource potential development processes”, “Resource potential practices”, “Resource potential approaches” , Hydropower resource potential techniques”
ACM	“Resource potential Management”, “Hydropower resource potential management approaches” , “Hydropower resource potential Evaluation”, “Hydropower resource potential development approaches” “Hydropower resource potential development techniques”, “Hydropower resource potential measurement”, “Resource Potential”, “Hydropower resource potential Analysis”, “Resource potential management methodologies”, “Hydropower resource potential methodologies”, “Resource potential Essentials”, “Resource potential methods”, “Resource potential development processes”, “Resource potential practices”, “Resource potential approaches” , Hydropower resource potential techniques”.
IEEE	“Resource potential Management”, “Hydropower resource potential management approaches” , “Hydropower resource potential Evaluation”, “Hydropower resource potential development approaches” “Hydropower resource potential development techniques”, “Hydropower resource potential measurement”, “Resource Potential”, “Hydropower resource potential Analysis”, “Resource potential management methodologies”, “Hydropower resource potential methodologies”, “Resource potential Essentials”, “Resource potential methods”, “Resource potential development processes”, “Resource potential practices”, “Resource potential approaches” , Hydropower resource potential techniques”.
Science Direct	“Resource potential Management”, “Hydropower resource potential management approaches” , “Hydropower resource potential Evaluation”, “Hydropower resource potential development approaches” “Hydropower resource potential development techniques”, “Hydropower resource potential measurement”, “Resource Potential”, “Hydropower resource potential Analysis”, “Resource potential management methodologies”, “Hydropower resource potential methodologies”, “Resource potential Essentials”, “Resource potential methods”, “Resource potential development processes”, “Resource potential practices”, “Resource potential approaches” , Hydropower resource potential techniques”.

II. RQ2: What kind of methodologies frameworks and approaches are used for exploiting and utilizing renewable energy resources

1) Search Strings/Second Step: Synonyms

a) Population

Citizens

b) Intervention

“Resource potential Management”, “Hydropower resource potential management approaches” , “Hydropower resource potential Evaluation”, “Hydropower resource potential development approaches” “Hydropower resource potential development techniques”

c) Outcome

“Hydropower trends around the Globe”, “Resource Potential Status”, “Status of Resource Potential Management”, “Current Resource Potential Status”, “Hydropower Resource Potential status”, ”Hydropower Resource Potential Trends and Status”

2) Strings Used for Essential “ Primary” Studies Search of Research Question 2

Table 2: What kind of methodologies frameworks and approaches are used for exploiting and utilizing renewable energy resources

Database	Search String
Springer	“Resource potential Management”, “Hydropower resource potential management approaches” , “Hydropower resource potential Evaluation”, “Hydropower resource potential development approaches” “Hydropower resource potential development techniques”, “Hydropower resource potential measurement”, “Resource Potential”, “Hydropower resource potential Analysis”, “Resource potential management methodologies”, “Hydropower resource potential methodologies”, “Resource potential Essentials”, “Resource potential methods”, “Resource potential development processes”, “Resource potential practices”, “Resource potential approaches” , Hydropower resource potential techniques”
ACM	“Resource potential Management”, “Hydropower resource potential management approaches” , “Hydropower resource potential Evaluation”, “Hydropower resource potential development approaches” “Hydropower resource potential development techniques”, “Hydropower resource potential measurement”, “Resource Potential”, “Hydropower resource potential Analysis”, “Resource potential management methodologies”, “Hydropower resource potential methodologies”, “Resource potential Essentials”, “Resource potential methods”, “Resource potential development processes”, “Resource potential practices”, “Resource potential approaches” , Hydropower resource potential techniques”.
IEEE	“Resource potential Management”, “Hydropower resource potential management approaches” , “Hydropower resource potential Evaluation”, “Hydropower resource potential development approaches” “Hydropower resource potential development techniques”, “Hydropower resource potential measurement”, “Resource Potential”, “Hydropower resource potential Analysis”, “Resource potential management methodologies”, “Hydropower resource potential methodologies”, “Resource potential Essentials”, “Resource potential methods”, “Resource potential development processes”, “Resource potential practices”, “Resource potential approaches” , Hydropower resource potential techniques”.
Science Direct	“Resource potential Management”, “Hydropower resource potential management approaches” , “Hydropower resource potential Evaluation”, “Hydropower resource potential development approaches” “Hydropower resource potential development techniques”, “Hydropower resource potential measurement”, “Resource Potential”, “Hydropower resource potential Analysis”, “Resource potential management methodologies”, “Hydropower resource potential methodologies”, “Resource potential Essentials”, “Resource potential methods”, “Resource potential development processes”, “Resource potential practices”, “Resource potential approaches” , Hydropower resource potential techniques”.

III. RQ3: What are the limitations of exploiting renewable resource potentials?

1) Search strings/Second Step :Synonyms

a) Population

“Citizens”

b) Intervention

“Resource potential Management”, “Hydropower resource potential management approaches” , “Hydropower resource potential Evaluation”, “Hydropower resource potential development approaches” “Hydropower resource potential development techniques”

c) Outcome

“Hydropower trends around the Globe” , “Resource Potential Status”, “Status of Resource Potential Management”, “Current Resource Potential Status”, “Hydropower Resource Potential status”, ”Hydropower Resource Potential Trends and Status”

1) Strings Used for Primary Studies Search of Research question 3

Table 3: What are the limitations of exploiting renewable resource potentials?

Database	Search String
Springer	“Resource potential Management”, “Hydropower resource potential management approaches” , “Hydropower resource potential Evaluation”, “Hydropower resource potential development approaches” “Hydropower resource potential development techniques”, “Hydropower resource potential measurement”, “Resource Potential”, “Hydropower resource potential Analysis”, “Resource potential management methodologies”, “Hydropower resource potential methodologies”, “Resource potential Essentials”, “Resource potential methods”, “Resource potential development processes”, “Resource potential practices”, “Resource potential approaches” , Hydropower resource potential techniques”
ACM	“Resource potential Management”, “Hydropower resource potential management approaches” , “Hydropower resource potential Evaluation”, “Hydropower resource potential development approaches” “Hydropower resource potential development techniques”, “Hydropower resource potential measurement”, “Resource Potential”, “Hydropower resource potential Analysis”, “Resource potential management methodologies”, “Hydropower resource potential methodologies”, “Resource potential Essentials”, “Resource potential methods”, “Resource potential development processes”, “Resource potential practices”, “Resource potential approaches” , Hydropower resource potential techniques”.
IEEE	“Resource potential Management”, “Hydropower resource potential management approaches” , “Hydropower resource potential Evaluation”, “Hydropower resource potential development approaches” “Hydropower resource potential development techniques”, “Hydropower resource potential measurement”, “Resource Potential”, “Hydropower resource potential Analysis”, “Resource potential management methodologies”, “Hydropower resource potential methodologies”, “Resource potential Essentials”, “Resource potential methods”, “Resource potential development processes”, “Resource potential practices”, “Resource potential approaches” , Hydropower resource potential techniques”.
Science Direct	“Resource potential Management”, “Hydropower resource potential management approaches” , “Hydropower resource potential Evaluation”, “Hydropower resource potential development approaches” “Hydropower resource potential development techniques”, “Hydropower resource potential measurement”, “Resource Potential”, “Hydropower resource potential Analysis”, “Resource potential management methodologies”, “Hydropower resource potential methodologies”, “Resource potential Essentials”, “Resource potential methods”, “Resource potential development processes”, “Resource potential practices”, “Resource potential approaches” , Hydropower resource potential techniques”.

4.2. Literature Publication Search Strategy

As hydropower resource potential is with diverse terminology so we decided to use the search string with different synonyms of hydropower resource potential such as “Sustainable energy resource”, “Hydroelectricity”, “Renewable energy source”, “Sustainable hydropower”, “Hydroelectric energy”, “Hydropower technology”, “Hydroelectric power “Literature published between 1993-2019 are selected to search by using only the title and keywords fields

4.3 “Inclusion” and “Exclusion “Criteria of Literature

“Inclusion” criteria include

(1) screened out the research study for resource potential trends and status “Exclusion” criteria

include

- (1) Eliminate research study about trends and status in other fields
- (2) Excluding copy sections, barring those without total information. Eliminate studies without full text.

5. DATA EXTRACTION / PUBLICATION QUALITY ASSESSMENT

For the information extraction the summary sheet was designed from the chosen literature. That will extricate the at finally chosen papers surveying their quality and searching answers for research questions

Quality Assessment Detail 1-5:

1. Literature provides detailed information of hydropower resource potential and resource potential management trends?

The possible responses to this question are: “Yes (a)” for the detail description of hydropower resource potential trends around the globe; “partially (b)” for the partial or not detail information about hydropower resource potential trends around the globe; and “No (c)” paper having no information about resource potential management trends

2. Literature gives the enough tenet as how the hydropower resource potential management procedures are applied across the globe?

The possible responses to this question are “Yes (a)” for having the information as how the hydro resource potential management techniques helped out across the globe; “partially (b)” paper having partial or not detail information as how the hydropower resource potential management techniques helped out across the globe; and “No (c)” paper having no information as how the hydropower resource potential techniques helped out across the globe.

3. The literature provides clear outcomes of hydropower resource potential management status for across the globe?

The possible responses to this question are: “Yes (a)” paper having clear outcomes; “partially (b)” for paper having partial or not detail results; and “No (c)” for paper having no outcomes.

4. The literature has been published in a relevant journal or conference proceedings?

The possible responses to this question are: “Very relevant (a)”; “Relevant (b)”, and “Not so relevant (c)”. This question will be evaluated by considering the order of significance provided by the computerized library, the CORE conference positioning (A, B and C conferences), and the Journal Citation Reports (JCR) lists.

5. The study has been cited by other authors?

The possible responses to this question are: “Yes (a)” on the off chance that the paper has been cited by more than five creators; “partially (b)” in case the paper has been cited by 1 to 5 (1-5) authors; and “No (c)” for no citation. This question was appraised by considering the Google researcher citations count

Table 4: Data Extraction and Publication Quality Assessment

Paper/Publication Title:	
Authors:	Year of Publication:
Reference Type: Journal/Conference/Thesis/Unpublished	Publisher: Science Direct /IEEE/Springer/ACM
Quality Assessment	(a) (b) (c)
Study provides detailed description of hydropower resource potential across the globe?	
The study provides the guideline as how the hydropower resource potential techniques are used across the globe?	
The literature provides clear outcomes of hydropower resource potential management status for across the globe	
The study has been published in a relevant journal or conference proceedings?	
The study has been cited by other authors?	
Data extraction for Questions	Answers
What are the resource potential influencing factors and problems encountered in management of hydropower resource potential across the globe?	Questionnaires
Which Hydropower Resource potential evaluation methods commonly used for evaluation?	User/researcher usability test Following existing guidelines Observation and interviews Statistical analysis through system log files
Which management technique/method has been reported in this study?	Technique /Method
Which kind of case study discussed in the paper?	Hydropower across the country Resource potential in developed countries Hydropower resource potential in developing countries Hydropower resource potential in under developed countries
Data characteristics	Academia Mixed Industrial Government
What are the limitations of hydropower resource potential management across the globe?	Hydrology dependency Low dissolved oxygen level generation Reservoir construction Perception variation Distributed Environment Others
Empirical Validation of the resource potential management techniques applied across the globe	Case Study Experiment Survey experience reports observational study, survey action research Others
Which classification of theoretical studies are mentioned here?	Design principles and ideas of resource potential management Evaluation method of hydropower resource potential management Development and influencing factor of hydropower resource potential management Design principles, ideas, and evaluation methods Development, influencing factor, and evaluation method of hydropower resource potential management

6. PUBLICATION’S GENERAL INFORMATION

Table 5 shows the general details of publications within the systematic study audit prepare all these papers were finalized to gather the information according to our designed questions.

Through searching of the literature for 27 years within the four databases, we got collective of 8035 published studies. After implementation of our “inclusion” and “exclusion” criteria, we considered 61 publications for analysis

Reasons for the high exclusion rate are as follows.

- 1) It happens commonly that repetition of same publication occurs in databases.
- 2) Unrelated field of study retrieved commonly.
- 3) Search function limitation by databases

Table 5: Information Regarding Databases Literature

S.No	Information Regarding Databases Literature				
	Title	Author	Database (Digital Library)	Journal/Conference/Chapter/Magazine	Year
1	Renewable energy deployment to combat energy crisis in Pakistan	Abdul Raheem, Sikandar Ali Abbasi, Asif Memon, Saleem R. Samo, Y. H. Taufiq-Yap, Michael K. Danquah and Razif Harun	Springer	Journal	2016

02	India-Pakistan Energy Cooperation: Rethinking Opportunities and Newer Approaches	Mahendra P. La ma	Springer	Chapter	2014
03	Global Expansion of Renewable Energy Generation: An Analysis of Policy Instruments	Sanya Carley, Elizabeth Baldwin, Lauren M. MacLean, Jennifer N. Brass	Springer	Journal	2017
04	The role of renewable and non-renewable energy consumption in CO ₂ emissions: a disaggregate analysis of Pakistan	Syed Anees Haider Zaidi, Danish, Fujun Hou, Faisal Mehmood Mirza	Springer	Journal	2018
05	Solar Energy: Topographical Asset for Pakistan	Pervez Hameed Shaikh, Faheemullah Shaikh, and Mushtaq Mirani	Springer	Journal	2013
06	Potential consequences of projected climate change impacts on hydroelectricity generation	Pierre Mukheibir	Springer	Journal	2013
07	Poverty, environment and economic growth: exploring the links among three complex issues with specific focus on the Pakistan's case	Himayatullah Khan	Springer	Journal	2008
08	An econometric analysis of inter-fuel substitution in energy sector of Pakistan	Waqar Khalid, Abdul Jalil	Springer	Journal	2019
09	The Future of Energy II: Renewable Energy	<i>Francis F. Chen</i>	Springer	Chapter	2011
10	Evaluating renewable energy sources for implementing the hydrogen economy in Pakistan: a two-stage fuzzy MCDM approach	Li Xu , Syed Ahsan Ali Shah, Hashim Zameer , Yasir ,Ahmed Solangi	Springer	Journal	2019
11	Developing High-Resolution Remote Sensing Technology	Kabiyeva Marzhan Kaskina Dina	Springer	Chapter	2018

	into an Advanced Knowledge Management System to Assess Small-Scale Hydropower Potential in Kazakhstan	Bradshaw Roland			
12	Modelling Water Resource Allocation: A Case Study on Agriculture Versus Hydropower Production	Jorge Bielsa Rosa Duarte	Springer	Chapter	2002
13	Study on Corrosion Status and Control Strategies in Energy Field in China	Jianyun Zhang	Springer	Chapter	2019
14	Applying rough random MODM model to resource- constrained project scheduling problem: A case study of Pubugou Hydropower Project in China	ZheZhang, Jiupin g Xu	Springer	Journal	2014
15	Hydropower	Jingsheng Jia, Petr as Punys Jing Ma	Springer	Chapter	2012
16	Small Hydropower Resources And Prospects Of Small Hydropower Electric Plants In The Near-Border Regions Of Ukraine	Igor Winkler	Springer	Conference	2009
17	Geospatial and hydrological modeling to assess hydropower potential zones and site location over rainfall dependent Inland catchment	Manish Kumar G tooya, Vishal Singh, Akshay H. Meena	Springer	Journal	2015
18	Utilization of the world's potential water resources by hydropower installations	G. A. Pretro M. P. Fedorov	Springer	Journal	1993
19	Adaptation to Climate Change in the Management of a Canadian Water-Resources System Exploited for Hydropower	Marie Minville François Brissette Stéphane Krau Robert Leconte	Springer	Journal	2009

20	Hydropower for sustainable water and energy development in Ethiopia	Dagmawi Muluge ta Degefu Weijun He Jian Hua Zhao	Springer	Journal	2015
21	The Current Situation and Perspectives on the Use of Hydropower for Electricity Generation	Jorge Morales Pedraza	Springer	Journal	2015
22	Harnessing Renewable Energy Technologies for ICT and e-Governance Services in Un-Electrified Communities in Rural Nepal	Mona Sharma	ACM	Conference	2012
23	Parasol and GreenSwitch: Managing Datacenters Powered by Renewable Energy	Inigo Gouri, William Katsak, Kien Le [†] , Thu D. Nguyen, Ricardo Bianchini	ACM	Conference	2013
24	Potential to reduce energy consumption and GHG emissions by using renewable energy technologies in the conversion of existing houses into net-zero and near net- zero energy buildings	S. Rasoul Asaee , V. Ismet Ugursal	ACM	Conference	2018
25	Application of Data Science for Controlling Energy Crises: A Case Study of Pakistan	Saif Ullah, Muhammad Asif, Shahbaz Ahmad , Ulfat Imdad, Osama Sohaib	ACM	Conference	2019
26	Leveraging Renewable Energy in Data Centers: Present and Future	Ricardo Bianchini	ACM	Conference	2012
27	The Case for Efficient Renewable Energy Management in Smart Homes	Ting Zhu ,A ditya Mishra, David Irwin, Navin Sharma, Prashant Shenoy, Don Towsley	ACM	Workshop	2011
28	Increasing Data Centre Renewable Power Share via Intelligent Smart City Power Control	Florian Niedermeier, Wolfgang Duschl , Torben Möller , Hermann de Meer	ACM	Conference	2015

29	HydroNode: An Underwater Sensor Node Prototype for Monitoring Hydroelectric Reservoirs	Luiz F. M. Vieira, David Pinto , Sadraque S. Viana, Marcos A. M. Vieira , José Augusto M. Nacif, Alex B. Vieira	ACM	Conference	2012
30	Energy Generation Capacity Analysis of a Canal Based Hydro Project	Farhan Khan , Kinza Ali, Ahmed Kausar , Shafaq Kausar	IEEE	Conference	2013
31	Energy outlook in Pakistan	Khuram Pervez Amber , Naila Ashraf	IEEE	Conference	2014
32	Cost Optimization of an Off-Grid Hybrid Renewable Energy System with Battery Storage for Rural Electrification in Pakistan	Rizwan Kamal, Muhammad Younas, Muhammad Shoaib Khalid, Affaq Qamar	IEEE	Conference	2018
33	Economic Evaluation of Tarbela Dam	Haris Mushtaq, Dr. Mohammad Bilal Khan, Hafeez Rehman Khan, Muhammad Ali Zahoor	IEEE	Conference	2015
34	A Micro Hydro Power Plant for Distributed Generation using Municipal Water Waste with Archimedes Screw	Ali Raza, Muhammad Saleem Mian, Dianguo Xu, Jawad Ahmed	IEEE	Conference	2013
35	Optimization of Daily Operation of Micro Hydro Power Plant Coupled with Compress Air Storage	Usama Bin Irshad, M.S Javaid, Saifullah Shafiq, Md Shafiul Alam, M.A Abido, Tahir Mumtaz	IEEE	Conference	2016
36	Extenuating Shortfall of Electric Power through Potential Accessible in Pakistan	Mariyam Arif , Ye Liu and Israr ul Haq	IEEE	Conference	2018
37	Grid Interconnection of Micro Hydro Power Plants: Major Requirements, Key Issues and Challenges	Waqas Ali , Haroon Farooq, Ata Ur Rehman, Mohsin Jamil, Qasim Awais , Mohsin Ali	IEEE	Conference	2018

38	A predictive pan-European economic and production dispatch model for the energy transition in the electricity sector	Laurent Pagnier, Philippe Jacquod	IEEE	Conference	2017
39	Thermal Unit Commitment considering Pumped Storage Hydro Electricity Plants	Mary Prasanna T, C.H. Ram jethmalani, Dr.Sishaj P Simon	IEEE	Conference	2013
40	Optimization of Capacity and Operational Scheduling for Grid- Tied Microgrid using Pumped-Storage Hydroelectricity and Photovoltaic	Petrus Yuri Nugraha, Augie Widyotriatmo, Sutanto Hadisupadmo, Deddy Kurniadi	IEEE	Conference	2015
41	Interaction between short-term and seasonal storages in a predominantly renewable power system	Christoph Groiss-Walter Schaffer, Wolfgang Gawlik	IEEE	Conference	2017
42	Developing and utilization of hydroelectric power and improving atmospheric environment	Maoyu Ran ; Yan Hu	IEEE	Conference	2011
43	Restless Waters: Fossil Fuel Emissions Conditioning a Reduction inHydroelectric Resources in Chile	Hugh Rudnick ; Rodrigo Palma-Behnke ; Andrea Rudnick ; Carlos Benavides	IEEE	Magazines	2014
44	Energy Scenario and Potential of Hydroelectric Power in Pakistan	Waqar Uddin ; Sadam Hussain ; Kamran Zeb ; Musaib Aleem Dildar ; Z. Ullah ; Ihsan Ullah Khalil ; R. Ullah ; A. Haider ; Muhammad Adil ; H. J. Kim	IEEE	Conference	2018
45	Assessment of renewable energy resources and the use of hydro power for fluctuation compensation in Cameroon	M. Pendieu Kwaye ; J. Bendfeld ; N. Anglani,	IEEE	Conference	2015

46	A review of current renewable energy activities in Bangladesh	Alimul Haque Khan, Kazi Rehnuma Zafreen, Mir Muntasir Hossain, Maidul Islam,	IEEE	Conference	2015
47	Prospects of rural electrification of Balochistan province with renewable energy sources	Anis Ur Rehman ; Syed Mushtaq A. Shah ; Syed Ali Raza Shah ; Saeed Badshah ; M.A. Khattak,	IEEE	Conference	2017
48	Feasibility and simulation study of high-rise building Micro-grid with PV and mini-hydro pumping	Jianmin Zhang ; Qianzhi Zhang,	IEEE	Conference	2013
49	Optimal Electric Energy Production scheduling for Thermal-Hydro Electric Power Systems	Jiekang Wu,	IEEE	Conference	2009
50	Interface model based cyber-physical energy system design for smart grid	Janet Roveda ; Susan Lysecky ; Young-Jun Son ; Hyungtaek Chang ; Anita Annamalai	IEEE	Conference	2011
51	“Water resources planning hydropower for sustainable and green energy in Turkey	Ibrahim Yuksel ; Hasan Arman ; Ibrahim Halil Demirel	IEEE	Conference	2018
52	Analysis of ways of solving the problem of hybrid energy complexes based on reserve for power supply of autonomous rural consumers in Myanmar”	Michael G. Tyagunov ; Thu Yein Min	IEEE	Conference	2018
53	“24 years postgraduate program renewable energy”	Evelyn Brudler ; Michel Golba ; Andreas Günther ; Hans Holtorf, Leonie Ibing, Edu Knagge, Udo Kulschewski			2012
54	Assessment of Hydropower Plants Energy Production Cost Influenced by	Ionut Bogdan Stoenescu ; Sorin a Costinas ; Gheorg	IEEE	Conference	2019

	Operational Decisions and Control Strategy	he Marius Deaconu“			
55	Flow regime aspects in determining environmental flows and maximising energy production at run-of-river hydropower plants	Alban Kuriqi, António N. Pinheiro, Alvaro Sordo-Ward, Luis Garrote	Science Direct	Journal	2019
56	Is the hydropower boom actually taking place? A case study of a South East European country, Bosnia and Herzegovina	Özge Can Dogmus, Jonas Ø. Nielsen	Science Direct	Journal	2019
57	Trans-regional transmission of large-scale hydropower: problems and solutions in receiving power grid	Jianyu Lu, Jianjian Shen, Chengguo Su, Qianqian Shen	Science Direct	Journal	2019
58	The energy injustice of hydropower: Development, resettlement, and social exclusion at the Hongjiang and Wanmipo hydropower stations in China	Xiaofan Zhao, Liang Wu, Ye Qi	Science Direct	Journal	2019
59	The Hydropower Potential Assessment Tool (HPAT): Evaluation of run-of-river resource potential for any global land area and application to Falls Creek, Oregon, USA	Thomas M. Mosier, Kendra V. Sharp, David F. Hill	Science Direct	Journal	2016
60	Resource assessment and feasibility study for the generation of hydrokinetic power in the tailwaters of selected hydropower stations in Nigeria	Laniyi L. Ladokun, Bolaji F. Sule, Kajogbola R. Ajao, Adeniyi G. Adeogun	Science direct	Journal	2018
61	Temporal analysis of water-energy nexus indicators for hydropower generation and water	Mohammed Basheer, Nadir Ahmed Elagib	Science Direct	Journal	2019

	pumping in the Lower Blue Nile Basin				
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[8,9,10,11,12,13,14,15,`16,17,18,19,20,21,22,23,24,25,26,27,28,29,30,31,32,33,34,35,36,37,38, 39,40,41,42,43,44.,45,46,47,48,49,50,51,52,53,54,55,56,57,58,59,60,61,62,63,64,65,66,67,68]

VII. Graphical depiction of analysed data outcomes and Specific Information related to existing literature

Q5: Source of Publication			Q6: Publisher		
Options	Response %	Responses	Options	Response %	Responses
Conference	52.45	32	Springer	34.42	21
Chapters	9.83	6	ACM	13.11	08
Journals	34.42	21	IEEE	40.98	25
Workshop	1.63	1	Science Direct	11.47	07
Magazines	1.63	1			
Total Responses=61	Answered Responses=61	Skipped=0	Total Responses= 61	Answered Responses= 61	Skipped=0
Mean=1.51			Mean= 2.393		
Standard Deviation=0.566			Standard Deviation=0.143		
Variance=0.321			Variance=1.243		
Standard Error=0.073			Standard Error=1.115		

Figure 1: Source of Publication

Figure 2: Publisher

Q8: Study provides detailed description of hydropower resource potential across the globe?		
Options	Response %	Responses
a	22.9	14
b	77.04	47
c	0	0
Total Responses= 61	Answered Responses= 61	Skipped=0
Mean=0.770		
Standard Deviation=0.424		
Variance=0.179		
Standard Error=0.054		

Figure 3: Study provides detailed description of hydropower resource potential across the globe

Q11: The literature provides clear outcomes of hydropower resource potential management status for across the globe		
Options	Response %	Responses
a	29.50	18
b	70.49	43
c	0	0
Total Responses= 61	Answered Responses= 61	Skipped=0
Mean=0.703		
Standard Deviation=0.459		
Variance=0.211		
Standard Error=0.059		

Figure 4: The literature provides clear outcomes of hydropower resource potential management status for across the globe

Q15: The study has been cited by other authors		
Options	Response %	Responses
a	93.44	57
b	6.55	4
c	0	0
Total Responses= 61	Answered Responses= 61	Skipped=0
Mean=0.9344262		
Standard Deviation=0.2495898		
Variance=0.6229508		
Standard Error=0.0319567		

Figure 6: The study has been cited by other authors

Q14: The study has been published in a relevant journal or conference proceedings		
Options	Response %	Responses
a	19.67	12
b	80.3	49
c	0	0
Total Responses= 61	Answered Responses= 61	Skipped=0
Mean=0.803		
Standard Deviation=0.401		
Variance=0.161		
Standard Error=0.051		

Figure 5: The study has been published in a relevant journal or conference proceedings

7. CONCLUSION

In this systematic review (SR) performed on resource potential management and hydropower resource potential around the globe , three research questions were established and research strings were designed using PICOC structure to extract research papers from different database, including ACM, IEEE, Springer, and Science Direct. Search protocol was designed for setting studies rules regulations to follow for summarize and concrete results after analysis.

On the basis of set protocols how the resource potential techniques are used around the globe for handling the hydropower resources while only 25 percent studies partially describe the techniques applications. In SR 75 percent study provides clear results of resource potential management status across the world, 25 percent are partially providing results of applications.

From these results, we found that so many researchers are doing studies on hydropower management. Their aim is to find out the existing constraints. They are also working on remedial techniques for management engineering for the hydropower. The aim of this study is to perform the active deep analysis of hydropower resource potential study across the globe Papers were chosen stress perceptive against every analysis question from these finalized databases 61 paper were chosen, these selected papers were analysed, assessed associate degree a based mostly by knowledge extraction was performed according to data extraction form . The collected data is statistically analysed by Statistical software “Spss” and according to this analysis, research papers selected for this study were taken between 1993-2019, out of 100 percent 34 % papers were published in journal 52 % in conference and 10 % chapters and 2% workshops and 2% magazines publications.

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